

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Itga11 is selectively activated during the first cell division of the human embryo.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We studied gene expression in the human embryo immediately after fertilization and zygotic activation and at the first cell division from 1-cell to 2-cell stage. We describe here identification of Itga11 as a zygotic cell factor required or important during the first cell division of the fertilized human embryo.

Citations

1. Coelho, L.F.L., Mota, B.E.F., Sales, P.C.M., Marques, J.T., de Oliveira, J.G., Bonjardim, C.A., Ferreira, P.C.P. and Kroon, E.G., 2006. Integrin alpha 11 is a novel type I interferon stimulated gene. Cytokine, 33(6), pp.352-361.